

Can someone make a better coding program that you can actually program things on, because currently there is no good coding program. All coding programs are fundamentally broken. Coding shouldn't be hard to learn or to make work. The reason I am uploading this file repetitively is because I am cursing myself by allowing an installation file on the main page of a website.